

Chief Executive Officers' Attributes and Transparency of Financial Disclosures: Evidence From Listed Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria

Festus AMALIKENEMECHI, Edirin JEROH, & Frank O. EBIAGHAN,
Department of Accounting, Delta State University, Abraka

Abstract

This research examined whether the level of transparency in financial disclosures of listed firms is influenced by the attributes of Chief Executive Officers (CEO). Attributes of CEO were measured using tenure, turnover, and ownership, whereas the level of transparency in financial disclosure was measured with reference to the Beneish M-Score. The study's focus was on listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria and secondary data which were extracted from the annual reports of sampled firms covered a 10-year period (from 2014 to 2023). The data were analysed by means of relevant robust estimation techniques. The results revealed that with a coefficient of -0.516595 and a p-value of 0.0004, CEO tenure (CEOT) has a negative and statistically significant effect on transparency, indicating that longer CEO tenure significantly reduces transparency. Similarly, with a negative coefficient of -0.237 and a probability value of 0.0101 this study also found that higher proportion of CEO's stake in the firms' ownership structure negatively affects the level of transparency in financial disclosure, indicating potential risks of concentrated control. Conversely, CEO turnover (CEOV) obtained a positive coefficient of 0.304093 (p-value = 0.0102), indicating that increased CEO turnover positively enhances transparency, likely due to leadership renewal and scrutiny. These findings underscore the critical role of CEO characteristics in shaping financial disclosure practices in emerging markets. The study thus recommends policy frameworks that mitigate risks associated with prolonged CEO tenure and concentrated ownership while promoting structured leadership transitions to foster investor confidence and market integrity.

Keywords: CEO Attributes, Transparency on Financial Disclosures, CEO tenure, CEO ownership, CEO turnover

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Several corporate scandals both at global and national levels have been linked to various activities of Chief Executive Officers (CEO), who at some point, were involved in some sort of fraudulent and sharp practices. This accounts for why studies in corporate reporting have attempted to examine the link between CEO attributes and organizational outcomes. By extension, the relationship between CEO attributes and transparency in financial disclosure has equally attracted significant attention from regulators, accounting practitioners, management, and scholars (Yahaya, 2022). Studies have shown that some CEOs exploit gaps in accounting standards and principles and manipulate or smooth financial statements across periods to meet specific objectives (Chulkov & Barron, 2024). Moreover, regulatory inadequacies governing the preparation and presentation of financial reports may further challenge CEOs' commitment to transparency (Bzeouich, Depoers, & Lakhali, 2024). As the most influential figures in their organizations, CEOs have privileged access to relevant operational information, which amplifies their capacity to shape financial reporting and, regrettably, to manipulate earnings to maximize their compensation.

Understanding the role of CEOs in shaping corporate financial practices is particularly critical in emerging markets such as Nigeria, where governance frameworks are still evolving. CEOs determine their firms' strategic direction and ethical standards, directly influencing the quality and transparency of financial disclosures (Angwaomaodoko, 2025). In an environment where stakeholders demand greater accountability, it is vital to examine how CEO-specific characteristics affect disclosure transparency, thereby fostering investor confidence and promoting sustainable business conduct (Aminu & Manko, 2024).

Transparency in financial disclosure is a concept that exemplifies the extent of clarity and completeness of the information content of financial reports (Amin, Feng, Guo, & You, 2024). Transparency in financial disclosure has become an increasingly important issue in Nigeria due to persistent regulatory challenges, making enhanced transparency essential for strengthening investor confidence and reducing risks associated with earnings manipulation (Shodeinde, Dada, Adegbe, & Akinola, 2024). Within this context, the Beneish M-Score, a well-established model that detects earnings manipulation using financial ratios, serves as a reliable proxy for evaluating the extent of aggressive accounting practices (Shakouri, Taherabadi, Ghanbari, & Jamshidinavid, 2021), and by extension, the extent of transparency in financial disclosure of firms.

Recent research highlights that CEO attributes including tenure, ownership, and turnover play significant roles in shaping financial reporting behaviours (Yahaya, 2024). For example, CEOs with longer tenure and diverse professional backgrounds tend to exhibit higher ethical standards and better decision-making, which correlate positively with financial transparency (Oyedokun, 2019; Kumar, Pillai, Kumar, & Tabash, 2023). Additionally, demographic factors such as ownership structure influence risk-taking and governance practices that affect disclosure quality. Given the distinctive corporate environment in Nigeria, examining how CEO attributes interact with organizational dynamics to enhance disclosure transparency is both timely and necessary.

Noteworthy, despite regulations aimed at promoting transparency in Nigeria, it may be possible that firms still engage in questionable reporting practices that may likely erode market integrity and investor confidence (Adegbe & Akinola, 2021; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024). This underscores the need to identify the specific CEO attributes that influence disparities in financial disclosure transparency across firms. Furthermore, since previous studies have largely measured transparency using earnings manipulation, accrual ratios, earnings quality, or timeliness metrics (Ogundele, Adeoye, Dada, & Bankole, 2024; Hassan & Yahaya, 2024; Bzeouich, Depoers, & Lakhali, 2024; Hsieh, Lo, Lai, & Ho, 2024); the present study attempts to extend prior empirical discourse by employing the Beneish M-Score, which offers a more objective and standardized measurement of financial transparency, addressing limitations in prior methodologies.

Accordingly, this study investigates the effect of CEO attributes on the transparency of financial reports among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria by specifically ascertaining:

- i. the effect of CEO tenure on the level of transparency in financial disclosures of listed Nigerian consumer goods firms.
- ii. the influence of CEO ownership on the level of transparency in financial disclosures of listed Nigerian consumer goods firms.

- iii. how CEO turnover affects the level of transparency in financial disclosures of listed Nigerian consumer goods firms.

By filling these critical gaps, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of CEO's role in promoting transparent financial reporting in an emerging market context.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CEO Attributes

CEO attributes to the distinctive qualities that characterize and shapes the leadership styles of CEOs within organizations. These attributes influence how CEOs drive the vision, and day-to-day operations of their respective organizations. Beyond internal management, CEO's attributes significantly affect how the company is perceived by external stakeholders. Key CEO attributes examined by previous studies include age, expertise, tenure, ownership, and turnover (Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020; Ukavwe & Jeroh, 2024; Obukata & Jeroh, 2025; Odechemu & Jeroh, 2025), each playing a critical role in shaping the transparency and integrity of financial disclosures.

Noteworthy, CEO attributes encompass both personal and professional characteristics that influence decision-making processes related to financial reporting and other possible outcomes. These attributes affect not only how financial information is managed internally but also how it is communicated externally, ultimately shaping stakeholder trust and perceptions of corporate credibility.

2.1.1 CEO Tenure

CEO tenure is a term that describes the duration a CEO has continuously held their position as chief executive within a firm. This attribute is fundamental in shaping both leadership effectiveness and the firm's financial trajectory. Longer tenures typically enable CEOs to implement strategic initiatives, develop comprehensive knowledge of the company's operations and culture, and cultivate market understanding (Emenyi, Akpan, & Okon, 2020).

No doubt, CEOs with shorter tenures may prioritize short-term financial results, potentially compromising disclosure comprehensiveness as they seek to meet immediate stakeholder expectations (Ukavwe & Jeroh, 2024). Frequent CEO turnover can disrupt consistency in strategies and financial reporting, undermining investor confidence. Thus, CEO tenure becomes a critical determinant of leadership stability and transparency, as sustained leadership supports accurate, consistent financial communication aligned with long-term business objectives (Angwaomaodoko, 2025).

2.1.2 CEO Ownership

CEO ownership reflects the extent of equity or shares a CEO holds, which aligns their personal financial interests with the firm's performance. A substantial ownership stake may be a motivational factor for CEOs to prioritize long-term growth and transparency in financial disclosures, as their personal wealth is directly linked to the firm's success. This alignment fosters a greater sense of responsibility, encouraging honesty and comprehensive reporting that builds investor and stakeholder trust (Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020; Sha, Shah, & Sarfraz, 2023).

In the Nigerian consumer goods sector, CEO ownership is especially pivotal given the pressures of regulatory oversight and the imperative for consistent financial performance. CEOs with significant ownership stakes may likely be more inclined to promote transparency, through the provision of clearer insights into financial health, strategies, and risks of their respective entities. This openness not only supports regulatory compliance but also signals strong corporate governance; thus, mitigating risks of earnings manipulation.

2.1.3 CEO Turnover

CEO turnover measures the frequency with which a company replaces its CEO through resignation, dismissal, retirement, or other forms of transitions. High turnover often signals organizational instability, resulting in fragmented strategic direction, disrupted operations, and inconsistent financial disclosure practices (Colak, Korkeamäki, & Meyer, 2024). Stable leadership, characterized by low CEO turnover, fosters continuity, supports long-term strategies, and cultivates trust among stakeholders (Chulkov & Barron, 2024).

Frequent CEO changes can lead to variability in financial reporting as new leaders bring differing priorities and disclosure styles, potentially causing confusion and eroding confidence in the reliability of financial statements (Huang, Villadsen, & Lu, 2024). Stakeholders may perceive high turnover as indicative of deeper governance or performance issues, prompting heightened scrutiny. Therefore, CEO turnover may significantly influence the consistency and transparency of financial disclosures, with leadership stability playing a vital role in establishing a culture of trustworthy and transparent reporting that enhances firm reputation and investor confidence (Bugaje, Taura, & Minjibir, 2024).

2.1.4 Beneish M-Score as a Measure of Financial Disclosure Transparency

The Beneish M-Score, developed by Messod Beneish, is a widely recognized analytical tool designed to detect potential earnings manipulation and fraud in corporate financial statements. This model uses a set of eight financial ratios derived from a company's financial reports to calculate a composite score, which indicates the likelihood of aggressive accounting practices or fraudulent reporting (Kumar et al., 2023).

The eight key ratios that were built into the model for computing the M-Score are:

1. Days Sales in Receivables Index (DSRI)
2. Gross Margin Index (GMI)
3. Depreciation Index (DEPI)
4. Sales Growth Index (SGI)
5. Leverage Index (LVGI)
6. Total Accruals to Total Assets (TATA)
7. Asset Quality Index (AQI)
8. Sales, General and Administrative Expenses Index (SGAI)

Each ratio captures specific aspects of financial statement behaviour that may signal irregularities, such as unusual revenue recognition, expense capitalization, asset valuation, or accrual patterns. The model was constructed using logistic regression and validated through principal component analysis to establish the predictive power of these variables in identifying financial distortions and by extension, the extent of transparency in corporate reporting. A

computed M-Score that is greater than -1.78 suggests high probability of manipulation whereas, M-score between -2.22 and -1.78 indicates possible risk of manipulation; thus, warranting further investigation. Conversely, where the computed M-score is less than -2.22, the implication is that the company is unlikely to be manipulating earnings. While it does not confirm fraud, its objective, quantitative approach offers a robust proxy for assessing the transparency of financial disclosures by highlighting red flags associated with earnings management.

Within the Nigerian context, where financial reporting quality and enforcement may vary, the Beneish M-Score serves as an effective standardized measure of financial disclosure transparency. By focusing on measurable financial anomalies, this model enhances the ability to evaluate the reliability and integrity of reported financial information, thereby supporting investor protection and corporate governance reforms.

2.2 Conceptual Model

Figure 2.1: CEO Attributes and Transparency of Financial Disclosure Model

Source: Researchers' Model (2025)

2.2. Theoretical Review

The Upper Echelon Theory (UET), developed by Hambrick and Mason in 1984, posits that the personalities, values, and experiences of top executives fundamentally shape their decisions and actions, which in turn influence the strategic direction and performance of their organizations. This theory is particularly relevant when analyzing CEO attributes such as tenure, ownership, and turnover. For example, a CEO's tenure contributes to a deeper understanding of the company's operations, culture, and market environment, shaping their leadership approach and decision-making processes (Cheng, Cummins, & Lin, 2017). Furthermore, UET suggests that CEOs with significant ownership stakes are more likely to align their decisions with the long-term interests of the firm, as their personal wealth is directly linked to the company's success (Amin, Feng, Guo, & You, 2024). CEO turnover also plays a critical role in organizational stability and strategic continuity, as frequent changes in leadership introduce new values and priorities that can disrupt ongoing strategies (Kalembe, Kaawaase, Nkundabanyanga, & Kayongo, 2024). Overall, the Upper Echelon Theory provides

a valuable framework for understanding how CEO characteristics shape both organizational decisions and financial transparency.

2.3 Empirical Review

Several studies from emerging markets have explored the impact of CEO characteristics on various aspects of financial disclosure and corporate reporting quality. In Egypt, Amin, Abdelmaged, Ibrahim, and Abdelfattah (2025) examined CEO attributes and their relationship with audit report lag using 587 firm-year observations from 2012 to 2019 across non-financial firms listed on the EGX100. Employing both Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and logistic regression methods, the study found that CEO attributes such as ownership, founder status, family ties, and CEO duality negatively affect audit report lag; thus, reducing delays.

In Nigeria, research has also focused on the role of CEO attributes in financial reporting outcomes. Musa, Latif, and Majid (2023) investigated how independent boards moderate the relationship between CEO characteristics and real earnings management using a sample of 292 firms from 2018 to 2021. Outcome from the research revealed that CEO financial expertise, compensation, and nationality significantly reduce real earnings management, thereby improving financial reporting quality in Nigerian firms. Similarly, Obazee and Amede (2019) and Tanujaya and Nuriah (2023) analyzed CEO tenure, gender, financial expertise, and ownership in relation to financial reporting timeliness within Nigerian firms. Their findings consistently showed that CEO tenure and gender positively relate to timely financial reports, while financial expertise and ownership had less significant effects.

Insights from Indonesia emphasize how CEO characteristics affect earnings management behaviours. Wijanarko et al. (2024), using data from 300 state-owned and private companies, found that CEO tenure significantly increases earnings management, thereby suggesting that long-serving CEOs might engage in less transparent reporting. Putra and Setiawan (2024) also analyzed manufacturing firms listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange and reported that CEO narcissism correlates positively with both accrual and real earnings management, whereas demographic factors such as gender, nationality, and founding family status correspond with stronger monitoring and ethical business practices.

In other emerging Asian economies, Ngo and Nguyen (2024) explored the impact of CEOs' financial and accounting expertise on financial reporting quality (FRQ) in Vietnam. Analyzing 2,435 observations across non-financial firms from 2016 to 2020, the study reported that CEOs with financial expertise tend to manipulate earnings more, which adversely affects financial reporting quality. Similarly, Abdul Wahab, Harymawan, Wardani, and Nasih (2025) investigated the implications of CEO busyness combined with military experience among directors on the readability of financial statement footnotes in Indonesia. The study's outcome indicates that military connections and busy CEOs negatively diminish footnote readability, emphasizing the interplay between CEO attributes and subtle facets of disclosure quality.

Similarly, Sharawi (2023) reported that in Egyptian firms, older female CEOs with financial expertise tend to enhance the quality of financial reporting, whereas CEO duality diminishes it. However, the moderating effect of board ownership was found to mitigate the negative impact of CEO duality. Similarly, Luong, Minnick, Rivolta, and Sham (2024) demonstrated that CEO social connections with audit committee members significantly influence firm transparency and financial report readability, with stronger connectedness improving disclosure transparency and firm value.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design, which is appropriate given its reliance on historical accounting data extracted from annual reports and financial statements. Also known as causal-comparative research, the *ex-post facto* design involves analyzing existing data to investigate potential cause-and-effect relationships without manipulating any variables. This approach enables the researcher to assess the influence of past events or conditions on current outcomes by examining events that have already transpired. The study population comprised the twenty-one (21) consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 31, 2023. From this population, a purposive sampling technique was used to select fourteen (14) firms, based on specific criteria outlined in the table below.

Table 3.1: Sample Selection Criteria

Sector/criteria	Number of firms
No of firms	21
Less: Consumer goods (non-available Data)	03
Less: Consumer goods (Incomplete Data)	04
Total sample size	14

Source: NGX (2023)

The final sample size represents approximately 66.67% of the total population, making it sufficiently representative of the twenty-one consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). Data for the study were sourced from the annual reports and financial statements of the selected firms, utilizing secondary data extraction methods. The variables collected include CEO tenure, CEO ownership, CEO turnover, firm size, and the Beneish M-Score, with the data spanning a ten-year period from 2014 to 2023.

To provide a comprehensive overview of the dataset, descriptive statistics were first conducted, outlining key measures such as the mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values. Pearson correlation analysis was also employed to explore the relationships between the independent variables (CEO attributes and firm characteristics) and the dependent variable (financial disclosure transparency as proxied by the Beneish M-Score). To address the main objectives of the study and control for potential anomalies in the data, the Robust Least Squares (RLS) regression technique was applied as the primary method of analysis. Based on the

theoretical literature and earlier empirical studies, the present study adapted the model of Ologunwab et al (2022) to express the econometric form of the model expressed as:

$$TFD_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEOW_{it} + \beta_2 CEOT_{it} + \beta_3 CEOV_{it} + \beta_4 FSIZ_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

The Apriori expectation based on the literature reviewed and related theories is stated as follows; $\beta_1 X_{1it} < 0$, $\beta_2 X_{2it} > 0$, $\beta_3 X_{3it} < 0$. The basis for this expectation flows from the outcome of the literature review and empirical findings.

Where:

- β_0 = Constant
- $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Slope Coefficient
- μ = Stochastic disturbance
- i = i^{th} company
- t = period

3.7 Description of variables

Table 3.1: Description of variables

Label	Variable type	Description	Measurement	Source
TFD	Dependent	Transparency of Financial Disclosure	Measured by Beneish M-Score	Shakouri, et.al (2021)
CEOT	Independent	CEO Tenure	Length of Time as CEO assume office	Asad et'al (2024)
CEOW	Independent	CEO Ownership	Measured by the proportion of shares CEOs have to total shares	Tanujaya, and Nuriah, (2023)
CEOV	Independent	CEO Turnover	If CEO is replaced, it is expressed as 1, otherwise 0	Farah, et.al (2021)
FSIZ	Control	Firm Size	This is expressed as log of total asset	Yahaya, Akinola & Mbah, (2022)

Source: Authors' Compilation (2025)

4.0 RESULTS AND DISUCSIONS

4.1 Data Analysis

The sourced data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis alongside various diagnostic tests. They are therefore presented below:

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics

The statistics include mean, standard deviation, Maximum, and minimum values for the individual variables. The Descriptive statistics of the variables are shown on Table 4.1 is presented thus:

Table 4.1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	CEOT	CEOV	CEOW	FSIZ	TFD
Mean	2.724638	0.289855	0.268862	7.822223	-0.005747
Maximum	8.000000	1.000000	2.793200	8.901600	1.996100
Minimum	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	6.489100	-3.626000
Std. Dev.	1.791171	0.455348	0.513746	0.579466	0.975894
Jarque-Bera	30.14012	27.23455	636.2781	4.835811	52.34593
Probability	0.000000	0.000001	0.000000	0.089108	0.000000
Observations	140	140	140	140	140

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

Table 4.1 summarizes the outcome regarding the descriptive statistics for key variables used in the study. The mean CEO tenure (CEOT) is approximately 2.72 years, with a range from 1 to 8 years, indicating variation in leadership stability across firms. The average value of CEO ownership (CEOV) stood around 29%, while CEO turnover (CEOW) obtained a mean value of about 0.27, reflecting changes in executive leadership. Firm size (FSIZ) has a mean logarithmic value of 7.82, showing moderate size variation, whereas the Beneish M-Score (TFD), used as a proxy for financial disclosure transparency, has a near-zero mean, indicating that, on average, firms do not exhibit high levels of aggressive earnings manipulation. The standard deviations reveal considerable variability in CEO tenure and turnover, while firm size is relatively consistent. The Jarque-Bera test statistics and associated probabilities indicate that most variables deviate significantly from normal distribution ($p < 0.05$), except for firm size which is closer to normality. The total of 140 observations across all variables provides a sufficient data set for robust statistical analysis. This descriptive overview lays the foundation for subsequent inferential analyses.

4.1.2 Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis is used to test the degree and direction of linearity between the dependent and independent variables. The result is therefore presented in table 4.2:

Table 4.2: Spearman Correlation

Cases	TFD	CEOT	CEOW	CEOV	FSIZ
TFD	1.000000				
CEOT	-0.001120	1.000000			
CEOW	-0.112040	0.145315	1.000000		
CEOV	0.100794	0.271536	-0.064500	1.000000	
FSIZ	0.205656	-0.040765	-0.017831	-0.106688	1.000000

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

The Spearman correlation analysis in Table 4.2 examines the strength and direction of the relationships between the key variables in the study. The dependent variable, financial disclosure transparency proxied by the Beneish M-Score (TFD), shows a very weak negative correlation with CEO tenure (CEOT) at -0.001, indicating little to no relationship. CEO ownership (CEOW) has a small negative correlation of -0.112 with TFD, suggesting that increased CEO ownership is modestly associated with less transparent financial disclosures. Conversely, CEO turnover (CEOV) has a weak positive correlation of 0.101 with TFD, implying that greater CEO turnover may slightly enhance transparency. Firm size (FSIZ) exhibits the strongest positive correlation with TFD at 0.206, suggesting larger firms tend to have more transparent financial disclosures. Correlations among independent variables show that CEO tenure and turnover are positively correlated (0.272), while CEO ownership has weak negative or negligible correlations with tenure and firm size. Overall, these results indicate modest associations between CEO attributes and financial disclosure transparency, supporting further regression analysis to assess their impacts rigorously.

4.2. Regression Result: Hypothesis Testing

To ensure that the regression estimates are valid for policy formulation, the robust regression analysis was adopted in line with the three hypotheses stated earlier:

Table 4.3: Test of Hypothesis 1

Dependent Variable: TFD

Date: 02/04/25 Time: 05:52

Sample: 2014 2023

Included observations: 140

Method: Robust estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.705410	0.149629	4.714399	0.0000
CEOT	-0.516595	0.145152	-3.558992	0.0004
FSIZ	0.327271	0.127054	2.575840	0.0100

Robust Statistics			
R-squared	0.590787	Adjusted R-squared	0.567171
Rw-squared	0.682994	Adjust Rw-squared	0.682994
Akaike info criterion	88.78191	Schwarz criterion	98.19915
Deviance	59144.79	Scale	26.37019
Rn-squared statistic	18.96204	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)	0.000076

Source: E-Views 9.0 (2025)

The regression results in Table 4.3 test Hypothesis One, examining the effect of CEO tenure (CEOT) on financial disclosure transparency (TFD) using robust estimation. The model includes firm size (FSIZ) as a control variable and is based on 140 observations from 2014 to 2023. CEO tenure has a statistically significant negative coefficient (-0.516595) with a p-value of 0.0004, indicating that longer CEO tenure is associated with decreased financial disclosure transparency, as measured by the Beneish M-Score. Conversely, firm size has a positive and significant effect (coefficient of 0.327, $p = 0.010$), suggesting that larger firms tend to have more transparent financial reporting. The constant term is also significant. The model explains approximately 59% of the variation in transparency (R-squared = 0.591), confirming a good fit. Robust Estimation was employed to mitigate the influence of outliers and heteroscedasticity, ensuring reliable coefficient estimates. Overall, these findings support that while larger firm size enhances transparency, increases in CEO tenure may negatively impact transparent financial disclosures in Nigerian consumer goods firms.

Table 4.4: Test of Hypothesis 2

Dependent Variable: TFD

Date: 02/04/25 Time: 06:11

Sample: 2014 2023

Included observations: 140

Method: Robust Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.111217	0.133000	-15.873810	0.0000
CEOV	0.304093	0.118345	2.569539	0.0102
FSIZ	0.000159	0.001146	0.138716	0.8897
Robust Statistics				
R-squared	0.515606	Adjusted R-squared	0.509963	
Rw-squared	0.531903	Adjust Rw-squared	0.531903	
Rn-squared statistic	6.602530	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)	0.010183	

Source: E-Views version 9 (2023)

The regression results in Table 4.3 test Hypothesis Two, which assesses the effect of CEO turnover (CEOV) on the transparency of financial disclosures (TFD) using robust estimation over 140 observations from 2014 to 2023. The coefficient for CEO turnover is positive (0.304093) and statistically significant with a p-value of 0.0102, indicating that higher CEO turnover is associated with greater financial disclosure transparency. Firm size (FSIZ), however, has an insignificant effect on transparency in this model ($p = 0.8897$). The model explains around 51.6% of the variation in financial disclosure transparency (R-squared = 0.516). Given the statistically significant positive relationship between CEO turnover and transparency, these findings suggest that increased CEO turnover in Nigerian consumer goods firms may prompt more transparent financial reporting, possibly due to enhanced scrutiny or changes in managerial practices with leadership transitions.

Table 4.5: Test of Hypothesis 3

Dependent Variable: TFD

Date: 02/04/25 Time: 09:14

Sample: 2014 2023

Included observations: 140

Method: Robust Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.781525	0.135528	5.766503	0.0000
CEOW	-0.237417	0.092271	-2.573037	0.0101

FSIZ 0.289798 0.115260 -2.514293 0.0119

Robust Statistics

R-squared	0.437980	Adjusted R-squared	0.412993
Rw-squared	0.510409	Adjust Rw-squared	0.510409
Rn-squared statistic	19.86251	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)	0.000049

Source: E-Views version 9 (2025)

The regression analysis in Table 4.5 tests Hypothesis Three, assessing the impact of CEO ownership (CEOW) on financial disclosure transparency (TFD) using robust estimation from 2014 to 2023 over 140 observations. The coefficient for CEO ownership is negative (-0.237417) and statistically significant ($p = 0.0101$), indicating that higher CEO ownership correlates with lower transparency in financial disclosures. Firm size (FSIZ) also has a significant effect, with a coefficient of 0.290 ($p = 0.0119$), suggesting larger firms tend to have more transparent financial reporting. The model explains approximately 44% of the variance in transparency ($R\text{-squared} = 0.438$), with robust statistics confirming the reliability of estimates. The negative relationship implies that in the Nigerian consumer goods sector, increased CEO ownership may be associated with less transparent reporting, possibly due to concentrated control reducing external accountability and incentives for openness.

4.3 Discussions and Policy Implications

4.3.1 CEO Tenure (CEOT) and Financial Disclosure Transparency (TFD)

The findings presented in Table 4.3 reveal a significant negative relationship between CEO tenure and financial disclosure transparency. Specifically, the coefficient of -0.5166 is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0004$), indicating that longer CEO tenures tend to reduce transparency in financial reporting. This supports the notion of managerial entrenchment where prolonged leadership may lead to decreased openness and higher information asymmetry (Yahaya, 2022; Angwaomaodoko, 2025). Larger firms, however, demonstrate increased transparency, with firm size showing a positive significant effect (coefficient = 0.3273, $p = 0.010$), consistent with existing literature that links firm size to greater regulatory scrutiny and stakeholder pressure for transparent disclosures (Aminu & Manko, 2024). These results highlight the necessity for effective governance mechanisms that mitigate the potential adverse effects of extended CEO tenure on disclosure practices.

4.3.2 CEO Turnover (CEOV) and Financial Disclosure Transparency (TFD)

As shown in Table 4.4, CEO turnover exerts a positive and statistically significant influence on the transparency of financial disclosures (coefficient = 0.3041, $p = 0.0102$). This suggests that increased CEO turnover is associated with enhanced transparency, possibly attributing to

refreshed leadership perspectives and increased scrutiny during transitions (Luong et al., 2024). The firm size variable in this model is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.8897$), indicating that CEO turnover has an independent influence on transparency beyond firm scale. These findings emphasize the importance of stable and well-managed leadership transitions supported by robust succession planning to sustain disclosure, continuity and quality.

4.3.3 CEO Ownership (CEOW) and Financial Disclosure Transparency (TFD)

Table 4.5 presents a negative and significant relationship between CEO ownership and financial disclosure transparency, with a coefficient of -0.2374 ($p = 0.0101$). This implies that higher CEO ownership may reduce transparency, likely due to concentrated control and diminished external accountability a finding aligned with concerns that excessive CEO shareholding might limit effective oversight (Sharawi, 2023; Amin, Feng, Guo, & You, 2024). Firm size again positively influences transparency (coefficient = 0.2898 , $p = 0.0119$). Policymakers and corporate governance stakeholders should consider balancing CEO ownership with other governance controls such as board independence and regulatory monitoring to safeguard disclosure quality and protect investor interests.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence that CEO attributes significantly impact the transparency of financial disclosures among Nigerian consumer goods firms. Specifically, longer CEO tenure is associated with reduced financial transparency, suggesting the potential for managerial entrenchment and decreased accountability. Conversely, higher CEO turnover correlates positively with increased transparency, highlighting the beneficial effects of leadership renewal and scrutiny on disclosure practices. Additionally, CEO ownership has a negative relationship with transparency, which may be attributable to concentrated control limiting external oversight. Firm size consistently emerges as a positive determinant of disclosure transparency, reflecting broader regulatory and market influences. These findings contribute to the growing literature on corporate governance by underscoring the nuanced roles that CEO characteristics play in shaping financial reporting quality in emerging markets.

5.2 Recommendations

- i. Given the negative effect of prolonged CEO tenure on the level of transparency in financial disclosure, it is recommended that Nigerian consumer goods firms adopt governance frameworks that limit excessive tenure without disrupting organizational stability. Boards should implement term limits or performance-based evaluations to prevent managerial entrenchment, while promoting leadership continuity that supports consistent disclosure practices.
- ii. The positive link between CEO turnover and transparency suggests that firms should develop robust succession planning policies to facilitate effective leadership transitions.

Regulators and governance bodies must encourage structured CEO handovers to minimize disruptions and enhance openness during periods of managerial change.

- iii. Since higher CEO ownership can reduce transparency, there is a need for balanced ownership structures that combine significant managerial stakes with independent oversight. Corporate governance mechanisms such as independent boards, shareholder activism, and regulatory scrutiny should be strengthened to counteract risks associated with concentrated executive control.

REFERENCES

- Abdul Wahab, E. A., Harymawan, I., Wardani, D. A. K., & Nasih, M. (2025). Military-experienced directors, CEO busyness and financial statement footnotes readability: evidence from Indonesia. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 33(1), 18-42.
- Adegbie, F. F., & Akinola, O. (2021). Corporate Governance and Financial Reporting Quality: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 16(4), 1-12.
- Amin, A., Ali, R., & Ur Rehman, R. (2024). CEO attributes and borrowing costs: exploring the moderating role of financial literacy. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 1-31.
- Amin, K., Feng, C., Guo, P., & You, H. (2024). CEO Facial masculinity and accounting conservatism. *Accounting and Business Research*, 54(2), 224-254.
- Amin, M. A., Abdelmaged, E. M., Ibrahim, A. E., & Abdelfattah, T. (2025). CEO characteristics and audit report lag: evidence from Egypt. *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*, 33(1), 32-67
- Aminu, I. Y., & Manko, B. A. (2024). Impact of Non-Financial Services by Listed DMBs on the Development of SMEs in Nigeria. *FUDMA Journal of Accounting and Finance Research [FUJAFR]*, 2(1), 191-205.
- Angwaomaodoko, E. A. (2025). Corporate Governance and Firm Performance: Investigating the Impact of Governance Structures on Economic Outcome. *Path of Science*, 10(12), 1001-1011.
- Asad, M., Akbar, S., & Mollah, S. (2024). The role of independent directors' tenure and network in controlling real-earnings management practices. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 1-29.
- Bugaje, S. Y., Taura, N. A., & Minjibir, I. S. (2024). Investigating the effect of CEO characteristics and financial reporting quality of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *African Banking and Finance Review Journal*, 18(18), 110–127.

- Bzeouich, B., Depoers, F., & Lakhali, F. (2024). Does ownership structure drive the effect of CEO overconfidence on earnings quality?. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*. Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAAR-10-2022-0265>
- Cheng, J., Cummins, J. D., & Lin, T. (2017). Organizational form, ownership structure, and CEO turnover: Evidence from the property–casualty insurance industry. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 84(1), 95-126.
- Chulkov, D. V., & Barron, J. M. (2024). Data on executive turnover timing and type for US top managers. *Data in Brief*, 54, 110436.
- Colak, G., Korkeamäki, T. P., & Meyer, N. O. (2024). ESG and CEO turnover around the world. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 84, 102523.
- Emenyi, E. O., Akpan, D. C. & Okon, I. (2020). The moderating role of agency theory on CEO attributes and firm value: Implications on consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *FUO Quarterly Journal of Contemporary Research*, 8(1), 17-30
- Farah, T., Li, J., Li, Z., & Shamsuddin, A. (2021). The non-linear effect of CSR on firms' systematic risk: International evidence. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 71, 101288.
- Hassan, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An examination of the relationship between governance practices and financial reporting transparency. *International Journal of Management Technology and Engineering*, 14(5), 64-85.
- Hsieh, C. H., Lo, H. C., Lai, Y. Y., & Ho, C. C. (2024). Exploring the Nexus between Executive Compensation and Disclosure Transparency: Evidence from Taiwan. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Accounting Studies*, 6(3), 55-70.
- Huang, T., Villadsen, A. R., & Lu, C. (2024). Does executive turnover affect government transparency? Leadership changes and environmental information disclosure in Chinese cities. *International Public Management Journal*, 27(2), 241-258.
- Kalembe, D., Kaawaase, T. K., Nkundabanyanga, S. K., & Kayongo, I. N. (2024). CEO power, audit committee effectiveness and earnings quality. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 14(3), 585-611.
- Kumar, P., Pillai, R., Kumar, N., & Tabash, M. I. (2023). The interplay of skills, digital financial literacy, capability, and autonomy in financial decision making and well-being. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 23(1), 169-183.
- Luong, H., Minnick, K., Rivolta, M. L., & Sham, S. (2024). CEO Connectedness and Firm Transparency. *European Financial Management*.

- Musa, A., Latif, R. A., & Majid, J. A. (2023). CEO attributes, board independence, and real earnings management: Evidence from Nigeria. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), 1–21.
- Naburgi, M.M., Ojo, L.O., & Oyedokun, G.E. (2024). Board Attributes and Risk Disclosure of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies Listed in Nigerian Exchange Group. *Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCJSS)*, 9(1), 40-56, a publication of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
- Ngo, D. N. P., & Nguyen, C. V. (2024). Does the CEO's financial and accounting expertise affect the financial reporting quality? Evidence from an emerging economy. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 22(3), 653-676.
- Obazee, U., & Amede, F.O. (2019). CEO Attributes and Timeliness of Financial Reporting. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 3(3), 12-23
- Obukata, E. J. & Jeroh, E. (2025). Chief Executive Officers' characteristics and creditworthiness of listed non-financial firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Current Practice in Accounting and Finance (JCPAF)*, 16 (6), 29-46.
- Odechemu, A. A. & Jeroh, E. (2025). Chief Executive Officers' (CEOs') expertise and the likelihood of earning management among banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Current Practice in Accounting and Finance (JCPAF)* 16(6), 14-28.
- Ogundele, O. S., Adeoye, E. T., Dada, O., & Bankole, O. E. (2024). Do CEO characteristics influence earnings management? Evidence from the Nigerian banking industry. *Adeleke University Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 8-21
- Oyedokun, G. E. (2019). Board characteristics and financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Accounting & Taxation review*, official Journal of the International Accounting and Taxation Research Group, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Benin, Nigeria.
- Oyedokun, G. E., & Nwaokolobia, B. O. & Andah, A, R. (2019). Board gender diversity and performance of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Financial Sustainability Reporting (RJFSR)* 4(2), 1-12. A publication of the Department of Accountancy, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science & Technology
- Oyedokun, G. E., Micah, E. E. M., & Gimba, J.T. (2020). Effect of Board Attributes on Dividend Policies of Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. A paper presented at British Academy of Management BAM2020 Conference at Alliance Manchester Business School, Manchester, United Kingdom, 2-4 September 2020.
- Putra, A. A., & Setiawan, D. (2024). Do CEO characteristics affect earnings management? *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 24(5), 1137-1155.

- Qawasmeh, S., & Azzam, M. (2020). CEO characteristics and earnings management. *Accounting*, 6(7), 1403-1410.
- Saleh, M. W., Eleyan, D., & Maigoshi, Z. S. (2024). Moderating effect of CEO power on ownership and performance. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 19(3), 442-461.
- Sha, Y., Shah, S. G. M., & Sarfraz, M. (2023). Short selling and SME irregular CEO succession: Witnessing the moderating role of earnings management. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 85, 163-173.
- Shakouri, M. M., Taherabadi, A., Ghanbari, M., & Jamshidinavid, B. (2021). Explaining the Beneish model and providing a comprehensive model of fraudulent financial reporting (FFR). *International Journal of Nonlinear Analysis and Applications*, 12(Special Issue), 39-48.
- Sharawi, H. H. M. (2023). The Impact of CEO Attributes on Financial Reporting Quality in Egypt: The Moderating Role of Board Ownership. *10(4)*, 39-73.
- Shodeinde, J. B., Dada, O. S., Adegbe, F. F., & Akinola, M. B. (2024). Forensic Accounting Techniques and White-Collar Crime in Nigeria Public Sector. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(3s), 1619-1629.
- Tanujaya, K., & Nuriah, S. (2023). Determinants that influence audit delay. *Global Financial Accounting Journal*, 7(1), 99-116.
- Ukavwe, G., & Jeroh, E. (2024). Chief Executive Officer (CEO) attributes and the value of quoted firms in Nigeria. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 6(6), 911-930.
- Wijanarko, A., Cahyono, A. N., Susilawati, M., Santoso, F., & Pardede, M. (2024). The Influence of CEO Tenure on Earnings Management. *Innovative: Journal of Social Science Research*, 4(3), 494-503.
- Yahaya, A. A., Akinola, O., & Mbah, S. (2022). The Influence of CEO Characteristics on Financial Reporting Quality: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 20(1), 1-15.
- Yahaya, P. D. O. A. (2024). The impact of independent directors on financial performance, with CEO tenure as a mediator. *Available at SSRN 5020716*.